

Three new records of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) from Azerbaijan

Tamara V. Nuruyeva^{1,2}, Nataly Yu. Snegovaya^{1,2}, Mahir M. Maharramov³

1 Institute of Zoology, Ministry of Science and Education of Azerbaijan, 115 A. Abbaszade str., pr. 1128, bl. 504, AZ1004, Baku, Azerbaijan

2 Western Caspian University, 31 Istiglaliyyat str., AZ1001, Baku, Azerbaijan

3 Nakhchivan State University, AZ7012, Nakhchivan, Azerbaijan

Corresponding author: Tamara V. Nuruyeva (aliyeva_t@mail.ru)

Academic editor: R. Yakovlev | Received 29 August 2024 | Accepted 17 September 2024 | Published 26 September 2024

<http://zoobank.org/A8DD7892-185D-4BDF-9B7E-7A1E5C354C4E>

Citation: Nuruyeva TV, Snegovaya NYu, Maharramov MM (2024) Three new records of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) from Azerbaijan. Acta Biologica Sibirica 10: 1047–1052. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13831356>

Abstract

New data on three species of spiders from Azerbaijan is presented. Of these, *Anyphaena furva* Miller, 1967 (Anyphaenidae) and *Dysdera tbilisiensis* Mcheidze, 1979 (Dysderidae) are recorded for the first time in Azerbaijan, and *Cyclosa algerica* Simon, 1885 (Araneidae) is new to the entire Caucasus.

Keywords

Araneae, new records, fauna, Caucasus

Introduction

Currently, about 750 species are registered in the spider fauna of Azerbaijan (Nuruyeva and Huseynov 2016, 2022; Huseynov and Nuruyeva, 2017; Otto 2022; Zamani and Marusik 2023, 2024; Nuruyeva and Snegovaya, 2023, 2024 a, b, c; Ponomarev et al. 2024; Khasayeva 2024 a, b). During the examination of spider material collected by the second author in Gobustan in 2023, and in Khachmaz and Ordubad in 2024, three spider species new to Azerbaijan were identified. Amongst them, one

species from the Araneidae is reported for the first time for the fauna of the Caucasus. This information is provided below and the three species are illustrated.

Materials and methods

The specimens examined are stored in the collection of the Institute of Zoology under the Ministry of Education and Science of Azerbaijan (IZBA). Images were taken using a Nikon SMZ 1270 microscope equipped with a Sony DSC-P8 camera.

Results

Family Anyphaenidae

Genus *Anyphaena* Sundevall, 1833

Anyphaena furva Miller, 1967

Figures 1, 2

Anyphaena obscura: Bösenberg, 1902: 258, pl. 24, fig. 373 (m; misidentified per Breitling et al., 2015: 67).

Anyphaena furva Miller, 1967: 292, fig. 7 (♂). – Miller, 1971: 64, fig. 4 (♂); Růžička, 2001: 46, figs 1–3, 7 (♂, ♀); Bauchhenss, 2009: 153, figs 1a–c, 2 (♂); Vidal and Taberlet, 2018: 9, figs 1–2 (♂).

Material examined. 1♂ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Khachmaz District, Nabran Vill., (N41°45'48.5" E48°40'20.5"; 0 m a.s.l.) 02.V.2024, N. Snegovaya.

Distribution. The species is known from France Germany, Czechia, Slovakia, Caucasus (WSC 2024). In the Caucasus, it was previously recorded in Adygeja (Ponomarev et al. 2012) and South Ossetia (Ponomarev and Komarov 2015). New record for Azerbaijan.

Family Araneidae

Genus *Cyclosa* Menge, 1866

Cyclosa algerica Simon, 1885

Figures 3, 4

Cyclosa algerica Simon, 1885: 21 (♀). – Levi, 1977: 79, figs 34–37 (♂♀); Breitling, 2020: 339, fig. 5A–B (♀); Lecigne, 2021: 18, fig. 10a–d (♂♀); Morano, 2023: 86, figs 53–54 (♂♀).

Material examined. 1♀ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Nakhchivan, Ordubad District, Agdere, (40.79651°N, 47.05372°E; 85 m a.s.l.), 17.VI.2024, N. Snegovaya.

Distribution. This species is distributed from Western Mediterranean to northern Iran (WSC 2024). New record for the Caucasus.

Figures 1–8. *Anyphaena furva*, male (1, 2); *Cyclosa algerica*, female (3, 4); *Dysdera tibilis*, male (5–8). 1, 3 – habitus, dorsal; 2 – palp, retrolateral; 4 – epigyne, ventral; 5 – bulb, retrolateral; 6 – same, prolateral; 7 – same, distal; 8 same, proximal. Scale bars = 1 mm (1, 3); 0,5 mm (2), 0,2 mm (4–8).

Family Dysderidae C. L. Koch, 1837

Genus *Dysdera* Latreille, 1804

Dysdera tbilisiensis Mcheidze, 1979

Figures 5–8

Dysdera tbilisiensis Mcheidze, 1979: 466, figs 3–4 (♂♀). – Dunin, 1992: 67, fig. 12 (♂♀); Mcheidze, 1997: 78, figs 73–74 (♂♀).

Material examined. 1♀ (IZBA), Azerbaijan: Gobustan District, Sundu Vill., (40.79651°N, 47.05372°E; 85 m a.s.l.), 17–18.V.2023, N. Snegovaya.

Distribution. Previously known only from Georgia [WSC 2024]. New record for Azerbaijan.

Discussion

In Azerbaijan, the genera *Anypaena* and *Cyclosa* are each represented by two species (Otto 2022), while the genus *Dysdera* includes 18 species (Otto 2022; Khasayeva 2024; Zamani and Marusik 2024). With the data presented in this article, the number of species within these genera has increased by one. Among the species of the genus *Cyclosa* recorded in the Caucasus, *Cyclosa oculata* (Walckenaer, 1802), which has been reported from the North Caucasus and Georgia (Otto 2022), has not been found in Azerbaijan.

Acknowledgement

The authors are sincerely grateful to Alireza Zamani (Turku, Finland) for confirming the identification of *Dysdera tbilisiensis* Mcheidze, 1979. We also wish to thank Alexander A. Fomichev (Altai, Russia) for useful comments on the manuscript and linguistic assistance.

References

- Bauchhens E (2009) Beiträge zur Taxonomie von *Anypaena furva* Miller, 1967. Contributions to Natural History 12: 153–159.
- Bösenberg W (1902) Die Spinnen Deutschlands. II-IV. Zoologica (Stuttgart) 14(2-4): 97–384. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.6508>

- Breitling R (2020) South European spiders from the Duffey collection in the Manchester Museum (Arachnida: Araneae). *Arachnology* 18(4): 333–362. <https://doi.org/10.13156/ arac.2020.18.4.333>
- Dunin PM (1992) The spider family Dysderidae of the Caucasian fauna (Arachnida Aranei Haplogynae). *Arthropoda Selecta* 1(3): 35–76.
- Huseynov EF, Nuruyeva TV (2017) *Sidydrassus* (Esyunin et Tuneva, 2002), a new genus of ground spiders (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) for the fauna of the Caucasus. *Zoology and Ecology* 27(1): 44–46. <https://doi.org/10.1080/21658005.2016.1260301>
- Khasayeva SI (2024a) The first record of *Dysdera armenica* Charitonov, 1956 (Araneae: Dysderidae) in Azerbaijan. *Bulletin of Science and Practice* 10(7): 61–64. <http://dx.doi.org/10.33619/2414-2948/104/07>
- Khasayeva SI (2024b) To the study of spiders (Arachnida: Araneae) of Shakhbuz district of Nakhchivan Autonomous Republic of Azerbaijan. *Munis Entomology and Zoology* 19(2): 738–748.
- Lecigne S (2021) A new species of *Sintula* (Linyphiidae), redescription of *Brigittea innocens* (Dictynidae) and eight spider species newly recorded for Turkey (Araneae). *Arachnologische Mitteilungen* 62: 11–34. <https://doi.org/10.30963/aramit6204>
- Levi HW (1977) The American orb-weaver genera *Cyclosa*, *Metazygia* and *Eustala* north of Mexico (Araneae, Araneidae). *Bulletin of the Museum of Comparative Zoology* 148: 61–127.
- Mcheidze TS (1997) Spiders of Georgia: Systematics, Ecology, Zoogeographic Review. Tbilisi University, 390 pp. [In Georgian]
- Mcheidze TS (1979) New species of spiders of the genus *Dysdera* Latr. (Dysderidae) occurring in Georgia. *Soobshcheniia Akademii Nauk Gruzinskoi SSR* 94: 465–468. [In Georgian]
- Miller F (1967) Studien über die Kopulationsorgane der Spinnengattung *Zelotes*, *Micaria*, *Robertus* und *Dipoena* nebst Beschreibung einiger neuen oder unvollkommen bekannten Spinnenarten. *Přírodovědné práce ústavů Československé Akademie Věd v Brně (N.S.)* 1: 251–298.
- Miller F (1971) Pavouci-Araneida – Araneida [Order Spiders – Araneida]. In: Daniel M, Černý V (Eds) *Klíč zvířeny ČSSR [Key to the fauna of Czechoslovakia]* 4: 51–306. [In Czech]
- Morano E (2023) La familia Araneidae Clerck, 1757 (Arachnida: Araneae) en al ámbito ibero-balear. *Revista Ibérica de Aracnología* 42: 67–118.
- Nuruyeva TV, Huseynov EF (2016) A new species of ground spiders of the genus *Pterotricha* Kulczyński, 1903 (Aranei: Gnaphosidae) from Azerbaijan. *Arthropoda Selecta* 25(2): 213–216. <https://doi.org/10.15298/arthsel.25.2.08>
- Nuruyeva TV, Huseynov EF (2022) A new species of the spider genus *Harpactea* Bristowe, 1939 (Araneae: Dysderidae) from Azerbaijan. *Zoology in the Middle East* 68(1): 86–90. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09397140.2021.1965070>
- Nuruyeva TV, Snegovaya NY (2023) Two new spiders species (Arachnida: Aranei) in the fauna of Azerbaijan. *Munis Entomology and Zoology* 18(suppl.): 1980–1983.

- Nuruyeva TV, Snegovaya NY (2024a) New records of spiders of the family Thomisidae (Arachnida: Araneae) from the Caucasus. *Zoosystematica Rossica* 33(1): 102–105. <https://doi.org/10.31610/zsr/2024.33.1.102>
- Nuruyeva TV, Snegovaya NY (2024b) *Cryptodrassus* Miller, 1943 (Araneae: Gnaphosidae) – the first record for the fauna of the Caucasus. *Caucasian Entomological Bulletin* 20(1): 61–63. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10869581>
- Nuruyeva TV, Snegovaya NY (2024c) New records of spiders (Arachnida: Aranei) from Azerbaijan. *Euroasian Entomological Journal* 23(1): 47–49. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15298/euroasentj.18.5.09>
- Otto S (2022) Caucasian Spiders. A faunistic database on the spiders of the Caucasus ecoregion. Version 02.2022. Available at: <https://caucasus-spiders.info/> (accessed 12 August 2024).
- Ponomarev AV, Kovblyuk MM, Chumachenko YA, Volkova DD (2012) Preliminary data on the fauna of spiders (Aranei) of the Republic of Adygea. In: Matisho GG, Khunagov RD (Eds) *Social-Humane and Ecological Problems of Development of Contemporary Adygea*. Collection of scientific papers. SSC RAS Publishers, Rostov-on-Don, 447–481. [In Russian]
- Ponomarov AV, Komarov YE (2015) Spiders (Aranei) of the Republic of South Ossetia. The South of Russia: ecology, development 10(1): 116–147. [In Russian]
- Ponomarev AV, Mikhailov KG, Shmatko VY (2024) Review of spiders of the genus *Tegenaria* Latreille, 1804 (Aranei: Agelenidae) of Ciscaucasia and the Russian Caucasus. III. New data on fauna and distribution, with material from neighbouring regions. *Arthropoda Selecta* 33(2): 273–287. <http://dx.doi.org/10.15298/arthsel.33.2.15>
- Růžička V (2001) The female of *Anyphaena furva* Miller (Araneae: Anyphaenidae). *Bulletin of the British Arachnological Society* 12: 46–48.
- Simon E (1885) Etudes sur les Arachnides recueillis en Tunisie en 1883 et 1884 par MM. A. Letourneux, M. Sédillot et Valéry Mayet, membres de la mission de l'Exploration scientifique de la Tunisie. In: *Exploration scientifique de la Tunisie*, publiée sous les auspices du Ministère de l'instruction publique. Zoologie – Arachnides. Imprimerie nationale, Paris, 55 pp.
- Vidal E, Taberlet J-P (2018) Découverte en France de *Anyphaena furva* Miller, 1967 (Araneae, Anyphaenidae). *Revue Arachnologique* 5(2): 9–10.
- Zamani A, Marusik YM (2023) New species and records of *Oecobius* Lucas, 1846 (Araneae: Oecobiidae) from Iran and Azerbaijan. *Journal of Natural History* 57(37-40): 1693–1709. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00222933.2023.2272356>
- Zamani A, Marusik YM (2024) New data on *Dysdera* Latreille, 1804 and *Harpactea* Bristowe, 1939 (Araneae: Dysderidae) of the Caucasus, with new species and records. *Zootaxa* 5397(2): 195–217. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.5397.2.2>
- World Spider Catalog (2024) World spider catalog. Version 25.5. Natural History Museum, – Bern. Available at: <http://wsc.nmbe.ch> (accessed 15 August 2024). <https://doi.org/10.24436/2>